

CULTURABLE MICROBIOTA OF MOSS BANKS OF THE BERTHELOT AND CORNER ISLANDS

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Mosses are among the few plants that can survive in the extreme conditions of the Antarctic. The study of the microbiota of the endosphere and rhizosphere of mosses is important for understanding the adaptation of these plants to extreme environmental conditions and climate change. This work aims to isolate and characterize bacteria associated with the endosphere and rhizosphere of different moss species. Moss bank samples of *Ceratodon purpureus*, *Pohlia nutans*, and *Warnstrofia fontinaliopsis*, collected on the Berthelot and Corner Islands during the 28th Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition, were used in the study. To isolate microorganisms from the endosphere, the mosses were previously surface sterilized. Conventional microbiological methods were used for the isolation of microorganisms. Identification was based on morphological, cultural, physiological, and biochemical properties and the 16S rRNA gene sequence.

Isolates that formed morphologically distinct colonies on dense media were isolated from the studied samples, and their properties were studied. Isolates have been identified: *Micrococcus* sp. Pn45 (from the endosphere of the shoot part of *P. nutans*, the Berthelot Islands), *Sporosarcina* sp. Cp72 (from the endosphere of the shoot part of *C. purpureus*, Corner Island), *Sporosarcina* sp. Wf13 and *Staphylococcus* sp. Wf139 (from the rhizosphere of *W. fontinaliopsis*, Corner Island).

Micrococcus sp. Pn45 grow at 4–42 °C, form large matte yellow colonies of regular shape. The sequence of the 16S rRNA gene of this strain (GenBank PQ475944.1) is characterized by a high value of identity with the sequence of the 16S rRNA gene of *Micrococcus alovarae* AE-6, *Micrococcus yunnanensis* YIM 65004 and *Micrococcus luteus* strains NCTC 2665 and DSM 20030. The studied *Micrococcus* sp. Pn45 differs from the described *M. alovarae* AE-6 in the lack of gelatinase activity and the metabolism of some carbon sources. *Micrococcus* sp. Pn45 is not capable of nitrate reduction and does not exhibit urease activity.

Sporosarcina sp. Cp72 grow at 4–30 °C, and *Sporosarcina* sp. Wf13 – at 4–37 °C. Both strains form large, regularly shaped orange colonies. The sequence of the 16S rRNA gene of strain Cp72 (GenBank PQ475947.1) is most similar to the 16S rRNA of *Sporosarcina ureae* DSM 2281 and *S. ureae* NBRC 12699, and of strain Wf13 (GenBank PQ473536.1) to the 16S rRNA of *Sporosarcina aquimarina* SW28. The strain Cp72 differs from the described *S. ureae* DSM 2281 by the colony color and metabolism of some carbon sources. The Wf13 strain differs from the described *S. aquimarina* SW28 in colony color, halotolerance, inability to reduce nitrate, and lack of urease activity. *Sporosarcina* sp. Wf13 produces auxin-like compounds when growing in nutrient broth with tryptophan and are capable of synthesis of siderophores.

Staphylococcus sp. Wf139 grow at 4–42 °C, they form large white colonies of regular shape. The sequence of the 16S rRNA gene of bacteria Wf139 (GenBank PQ475948.1) is the most identical to 16S rRNA of *Staphylococcus edaphicus* CCM 8730, *Staphylococcus saprophyticus* subsp. *Saprophyticus* ATTC 15305, *Staphylococcus pseudoxylosus* S04009. The strain Wf139 differs from the described *S. edaphicus* P5085 in its inability to reduce nitrate and metabolize some carbon sources. *Staphylococcus* sp. Wf139 have urease activity and do not liquefy gelatin.

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